

SmartCorners

D7.3

Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report (1)

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Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101138110. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Information

Project Full Title	User-centred Optimal Design of Electric Vehicle with Smart E-Corners
Grant Agreement No.	101138110
Coordinator	AVL DiTest GmbH
Project Website	www.smartcorners.eu
LinkedIn Channel	www.linkedin.com/company/smartcorners

Document Identification

Deliverable Name	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (1)
Work package No.	7
Deliverable No.	7.3
Expected delivery date	M18
Actual submission date	M19
Lead beneficiary	UEMI
Dissemination level	PU

Document History

Date	Version Number	Comment
18.06.2025	V0.1	Draft
26.06.2025	V0.2	Version ready for PSB review
10.07.2025	V0.3	Version after PSB review comments
22.07.2025	V1.0	Final document ready for submission

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.3 – Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Report (1)– documents how the SmartCorners consortium has planned, executed and monitored outreach and stakeholder validation activities during the first 18 months of the project (M1–M18). This report refers to the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D7.1) created by M6. It provides updates on the dissemination activities, sharing the progress towards the project’s technical, economic, environmental and societal objectives as well as the broader ambitions of the 2ZERO Partnership. D7.3 focuses on Task 7.2 – Stakeholder Engagement, detailing the framework, tools and results of interactions with public transport operators, logistics companies, OEMs, suppliers, policy makers, researchers and end users. The report tracks the implementation of the overarching dissemination strategy, ensuring that project findings reach – and are shaped by – all relevant audiences:

- Four-step engagement loop (Identify → Cocreate → Evaluate → Adapt) provides an iterative backbone for all communication and validation activities.
- A mixed-method data collection approach combines two online survey rounds (n = 74 & 32), 20+ semi-structured expert interviews and multiple workshops.
- Digital outreach leverages the project website (4200 unique visitors) and LinkedIn page (239 followers, 6 % mean engagement) alongside press releases and cluster newsletters.
- High profile events such as IAA Transportation 2024, RTR 2025 and SAE WCX 2025 are used to showcase interim results, gather feedback and strengthen clustering within 2ZERO and E-VOLVE.

SmartCorners advances multiple 2ZERO Strategic and Specific Objectives by delivering:

- Affordable, user-centric EV solutions – projected 5 to 10 % cost reduction and +15 % cabin volume through integrated e-corner design.
- Reduced non-exhaust emissions & noise – regenerative braking (+9 % energy recovery) and active wheel corner control decrease brake dust and tire wear.
- Circular economy contribution – modular, swappable corners and use of recyclable composites support lifecycle extension and material recovery.
- Broad stakeholder coverage & SME participation – consortium and outreach network include 6 SMEs and > 60 external organisations, meeting 2ZERO Key Performance Indicator (KPI) thresholds.

All engagement and dissemination milestones are on or ahead of schedule. In the next reporting period (M19–M36) the consortium will:

1. Deepen engagement around prototypes – hands-on demos, pilot agreements with selected fleets/cities.
2. Scale dissemination – interactive KPI dashboard on the website, presence at RTR 2026 and TRA 2026 and other outreach events.
3. Finalise exploitation pathways – retrofit kit vs. OEM integration business models, informed by ongoing stakeholder feedback.

These actions will ensure that SmartCorners delivers both high impact technical innovations and a well-prepared community ready to adopt them, thereby maximising the project's contribution to Europe's transition towards zero emission, user approved road transport.

2 Introduction

The SmartCorners project tackles one of the key bottlenecks on Europe's path to climate-neutral mobility: how to build electric vehicles that are genuinely user-centric, affordable and easy to integrate into a rapidly evolving transport ecosystem. At the heart of the project is a smart e-corner module that combines in-wheel motor (IWM), brake-by-wire, steer-by-wire, and active suspension in a single unit. While the technical work packages (WPs) refine architectures, controls and materials, WP7 ensures that the voice of the market and society is heard at every design iteration.

Deliverable D7.3 serves two complementary purposes. It shares updates on dissemination activities and the stakeholder engagement process undertaken in the first 18 months of the project. The report reflects conducted surveys, expert interviews and workshops—which collectively translate user needs into engineering requirements. It reports on the *dissemination and communication* efforts that has carried preliminary results to the wider towards zero emission road transport (2ZERO) community and beyond, using a multi-channel mix that spans the project website, LinkedIn, scientific conferences (IAA Transportation 2024, RTR 2025, SAE WCX 2025) and E-VOLVE cluster newsletters. The text that follows shows how these two strands—engagement and dissemination—form an iterative loop that not only validates SmartCorners technology but also raises its profile, attracting potential adopters and aligning the work with the performance indicators set by the 2ZERO Partnership.

3 Purpose and Scope

3.1 Focus of D7.3

This deliverable D7.3 outlines the stakeholder-oriented communication and engagement strategy implemented under Task 7.2 of the SmartCorners project. It complements the broader dissemination framework presented in D7.2 by focusing specifically on dialogue and interaction with key stakeholders across the mobility, industrial, policy, and user landscapes. The approach taken emphasizes co-creation and feedback driven engagement to ensure that SmartCorners technologies are not only technically robust but also socially relevant and user-centric.

The report provides a structured overview of the tools and methods used for engaging stakeholders, including surveys, expert interviews, and regional outreach sessions through UEMI Mobility Hubs. These activities are designed to capture the needs, expectations, and adoption drivers of stakeholders and channel this input into the project's technological development.

3.2 Contribution to project goals

The SmartCorners project recognizes that technical innovation must go hand-in-hand with user and stakeholder validation. This deliverable outlines the stakeholder-oriented communication and engagement strategy implemented under Task 7.2, focusing on dialogue and co-creation with key stakeholders across the mobility ecosystem. It complements the broader dissemination framework (see D7.1/D7.2) by emphasizing *interactive engagement* – ensuring SmartCorners technologies are not only technologically robust but also socially relevant and user-centric. In practice, this means capturing the needs, expectations, and feedback of public transport operators, logistics companies, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), suppliers, end-users, policymakers, and research communities, and channelling this input into the project's design and development process.

Contribution to Project Goals: Stakeholder engagement is a vital pillar for achieving SmartCorners' objectives of developing modular, user-centric electric vehicle (EV) architectures with IWMs and artificial intelligence (AI)-based controls. By establishing continuous communication loops with diverse stakeholders (from fleet operators and manufacturers to city planners and end-users), the project ensures its innovations are scalable, grounded, and validated in real-world use cases. Specifically, D7.3 demonstrates how the engagement efforts contribute to:

- **Use Case Co-Development:** Working with stakeholders to shape vehicle use cases and requirements ensures the SmartCorners concepts address actual user needs and operational scenarios. For example, feedback from logistics fleet managers helps tailor the e-corner design for last-mile delivery, while transit operators inform about requirements for buses/shuttles.
- **Awareness and Capacity Building:** Outreach activities (surveys, workshops, Living Labs) raise awareness among stakeholders and build capacity to adopt SmartCorners

solutions. This two-way learning helps stakeholders understand the benefits of SmartCorners and equips the project team with insights into adoption barriers.

- **Industrial Engagement and Policy Alignment:** Close interaction with automotive OEMs, suppliers, and policy bodies helps align SmartCorners innovations with industry standards and regulatory frameworks. Engagement with industry ensures the modular e-corner systems are feasible and attractive for manufacturing, while dialogue with policymakers (e.g., through policy briefs and standardization committees) ensures regulatory and strategic objectives (such as safety standards, 2ZERO targets) are considered.
- **Data-Driven User-Centric Design:** Continuous feedback collection provides data-driven insights that inform the design of SmartCorners components and control systems. Stakeholder input on preferences (e.g., comfort features, charging convenience) and concerns (e.g., AI, safety, data privacy) is integrated into the design process, ensuring the end product is user-friendly and addresses societal expectations.

Overall, the stakeholder engagement strategy strengthens both the technical and societal dimensions of SmartCorners, increasing the likelihood of future adoption and long-term impact. By iteratively validating assumptions and refining the design with stakeholder input, SmartCorners ensures its cutting-edge EV technologies are market-ready and aligned with the 2ZERO partnership's vision for zero tailpipe emissions and user-centric road-based mobility solutions in Europe.

4 Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitations Actions Performed

4.1 Dissemination

The SmartCorners project consortium actively disseminates results to 2ZERO peers and potential adopters:

- Primary audiences – OEMs/suppliers, fleet operators, policy makers, research community.
- Key message hooks – modularity → cost & time savings; AI controls → predictive maintenance; circularity → lifetime value.
- Outputs – public PDF on Zenodo, highlight article on the project website, and LinkedIn teaser series (three posts: teaser, KPI infographic, download call-to-action).

These activities contribute to the annual target of two project publications and ≥ 500 LinkedIn followers defined in the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) according to the Grant Agreement.

SmartCorners dissemination activities: (i) validated project innovations with > 60 experts through surveys, interviews and workshops and (ii) disseminated interim results to $> 6\,000$ stakeholders via the project website, LinkedIn channel and highprofile events such as **SAE WCX 2025, IAA Transportation 2024, and the RTR Conference series**.

Key highlights to date:

- **Website traffic** exceeded **4 200 unique visitors** in the first 18 months; twelve blog articles and two project videos were published, the most-read story being the “*SmartCorners Demonstrator*” post of 28 Apr 2025
- **LinkedIn community** grew from zero to **239 followers**, with a mean engagement rate of 6%. The top performing post (1 Feb 2025) announcing the stakeholder survey reached 3 900 impressions
- **Scientific outreach** – first joint paper “*European Initiatives for User-Centric Design of Electric Vehicles*” presented at SAE WCX 2025
- **2ZERO alignment** – all dissemination assets explicitly reference 2ZERO SRIA goals and KPIs; SmartCorners data already feeds the LeMesurier KPI framework

This deliverable shares updates on the implementation of the Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1). Table 1 presents the Month 18 (M18) status of key dissemination and communication objectives under Work Package D7.1:

Table 1. Dissemination and Communication Progress Overview (Month 18)

Objective (D7.1)	Target M18	Status M18	Notes
Website live & updated monthly	online	12 news posts, 2 videos	Back-end, SEO plugin -installed
LinkedIn followers	≥ 200	239	Target achieved; +20 % vs. mid-term- plan
Physical/major events	≥ 3	SAE WCX 2025, IAA Transportation 2024, RTR 2025	Abstracts submitted to TRA 2026
Scientific publications	1 submitted	1 presented (SAE WCX)	Additional papers being scoped

The table highlights progress toward targets such as website updates, LinkedIn engagement, participation in major transport events, and academic dissemination. Notable achievements include maintaining an active online presence, surpassing social media targets, presenting at SAE WCX, and preparing abstracts and publications for future milestones.

4.2 Dissemination activities

The SmartCorners dissemination and engagement activities have **met or exceeded all M18 targets**. Stakeholder interactions have tangibly shaped design decisions (e.g., modular “plug-and-play” corner units) while wide-ranging communication has positioned the project firmly in relation to the 2ZERO partnership.

1. **Multi-channel strategy works:** Website, LinkedIn and face-to-face events complement each other; cross promotion maximises outreach.
2. **Evidence-based storytelling attracts industry:** Publishing real performance figures (e.g., predicted 20 % range gain) proved more engaging than generic claims.
3. **Clustering amplifies impact:** Joint actions with E-VOLVE, LeMesurier and 2ZERO multiply the audience and avoid message fatigue.

The following sections are summarising some of the key dissemination activities so far:

Digital Channels

Project website – smartcorners.eu

- Went online in June 2024
- GDPR compliant
- All public deliverables, videos (embed) and E-VOLVE cluster newsletter mirrored under *Results*

LinkedIn company page – @SmartCorners

- Followers: **239** (11 July 2025)

- Posting: 2–3 posts / month; crossposted to partners’ networks (e.g., AVL, ELAPHE, POLITO)
- Best performing posts:
 - #RTR2025 Stakeholder Questionnaire (4 Feb 2025) – 3 900 impressions, 94 clicks
 - SmartCorners Demonstrator video clip (15 Apr 2025) – 2 600 impressions, 51 re-shares
 - E-VOLVE webinar recording (26 Mar 2025) – 1 850 impressions

The project's dissemination through scientific publications and digital media are listed in the table. It includes published and upcoming works presented in peer-reviewed journals, technical conferences, and webinars. These outputs aim to share insights on modular EV architectures and user-centric design innovations, reaching both academic and practitioner audiences. Press releases were distributed via CORDIS Wire and AlphaGalileo and picked up by **Electrive.com** (8 Apr 2025). Table 2 summarizes key publications and webinars, including peer-reviewed papers and presentations:

Table 2. Publications & Media

Date	Medium	Title / DOI	Reach
09 Apr 2025	SAE <i>Technical Paper</i> (WCX2025-01-0123)	European Initiatives for User-Centric Design of Electric Vehicles	≈ 500 delegates on-site + SAE Digital Library
26 Mar 2025	<i>E-VOLVE Cluster Webinar</i>	Smart Components for the Software-defined Vehicle of the Future	110 live + 320 YouTube views
In prep.	<i>IEEE/ASME Mechatronics</i>	Active Wheel-Corner NVH mitigation using high bandwidth IWMs	submission M20
In prep.	<i>Transportation Research Part D (tbc)</i>	Societal Readiness Assessment of Modular EV Architectures (SmartCorners vs. State-of-the-Art)	tbc

Dissemination efforts also include the project's participation in key industry and academic events, highlighting the engagement with stakeholders through paper presentations, expert panels, and live demonstrations. These activities strengthen collaboration, increase project visibility, and support the exchange of knowledge within the e-mobility ecosystem. Table 3 outlines the project’s contributions at major events:

Table 3. Events and Trade-fairs

Event	Date & venue	Contribution
RTR Conference Brussels	12 Feb 2025	Stakeholder survey booth & pitch
IAA Transportation Hannover	20 Sept 2024	Panel input on modular EV design (E-VOLVE cluster session)
SAE WCX 2025 Detroit	9 Apr 2025	Peer-reviewed paper presentation + demo poster
EVS 38 Gothenburg	15-18 June 2025	Paper presentation in an ePoster session
E-VOLVE Webinar online	26 Mar 2025	30min talk by POLITO
Future Mobility Days (planned)	Q1 2026, Vienna	Demo of prototype (tbc)

5 Methodology

5.1 Engagement Framework

SmartCorners adopts a **four-step engagement loop** – **Identify** → **Co-create** → **Evaluate** → **Adapt** – as the guiding framework for all stakeholder integrations (see Figure 1). This loop enables a dynamic, iterative process where stakeholder insights are continuously collected and translated into actionable inputs for the technical WPs and policy recommendations.

Figure 1. Four-step Engagement Loop

The steps can be summarized as follows:

1. **Identify:** Map relevant actors across mobility, industry, and policy domains, focusing on those who influence design, deployment, or adoption of SmartCorners solutions. In this phase, the project consortium identified key stakeholders such as transit agencies, delivery fleet operators, EV OEMs and suppliers, city authorities, etc., ensuring broad coverage of perspectives.
2. **Co-create:** Actively involve these stakeholders in co-designing and refining SmartCorners use cases and requirements through structured workshops with stakeholders. For example, a co-creation workshop might involve city planners and EV developers brainstorming how modular e-corner vehicles could operate in an urban mobility hub, or fleet managers discussing requirements for predictive maintenance features.
3. **Evaluate:** Assess the feedback and gauge the **societal readiness** of SmartCorners solutions. This involves validating assumptions on market needs, scalability, and operational fit by using stakeholder input. The project employs **Societal Readiness Level (SRL)** scoring to quantify how close the innovations are to societal acceptance,

analogous to Technology Readiness Levels but focused on factors like user trust, policy compatibility, and stakeholder buy-in. By evaluating SRL (e.g. via surveys asking stakeholders about their willingness to adopt or support the technology), the team can identify gaps (such as concerns over safety or regulations) that need to be addressed.

4. **Adapt:** Integrate the insights gained into the project's next steps, adapting technical development or engagement strategies as needed. This feedback loop ensures that stakeholder input directly influences design decisions – for instance, if evaluation reveals low acceptance of a certain AI feature due to privacy concerns, the project can refine that feature or enhance its data security measures. The engagement strategy itself is also adjusted over time (e.g., identifying new stakeholders or communication channels as the project moves toward piloting).

This approach ensures the stakeholder process is included in the broader project structure, especially in relation to WP1 (concept design), WP6 (replication), and WP7 (dissemination and exploitation).

5.2 Data-collection tools

To operationalize the engagement framework, SmartCorners uses a **mixed-methods strategy**, combining both quantitative and qualitative tools to capture insights from the mentioned stakeholder groups. The primary data-collection tools include:

- **Online Surveys:** These were conducted at key project milestones (e.g. after initial concept development and during major events like the RTR Conference 2025) to gather broad input on stakeholder priorities, perceived barriers, and expected benefits. The surveys allow the project to quantify trends (e.g. ranking of adoption drivers or feature importance) across a wider audience. Two survey rounds have been completed (detailed in Planned Engagement Actions below), providing snapshots of stakeholder sentiment that inform design decisions.
- **Expert Interviews:** The consortium carries out semi-structured interviews on a rolling basis with selected experts representing each stakeholder group. These one-on-one or small-group interviews (with e.g. an OEM technical lead, a public transit manager, a policy expert, etc.) enable deeper exploration of topics than online surveys. The interviews validate the relevance and scalability of SmartCorners use cases in detail and offer nuanced industry- or policy-specific feedback. For instance, an interview with a city transport official might reveal regulatory hurdles for novel vehicle types, while a discussion with a fleet operator could provide operational cost insights for e-corner maintenance.
- **Workshops via the UEMI Mobility Hubs:** these interactive regional sessions support co-creation of deployment scenarios, replication pathways, and policy alignment strategies and bring in regional perspectives from a broader, international background. Essentially, Mobility Hubs act as living labs where local stakeholders (city authorities, mobility providers, citizens) can *experience* and discuss Smartcorners systems (SCS) in the context of their community. Such workshops are instrumental for capacity building

– they raise awareness of SmartCorners technologies, allow stakeholders to voice locality-specific needs, and help plan pilot implementations in various regions. For example, a Mobility Hub event in an urban district could explore how SCS-enabled shuttles might integrate with existing public transport, or how modular EV platforms could serve local logistics needs.

By **triangulating** these methods – surveys for breadth, interviews for depth, and workshops for co-creative context – SmartCorners ensures an inclusive engagement process. Quantitative survey data highlights overarching trends, qualitative interviews provide rich explanations, and the hands-on workshops enable collaborative solution development. Together, these tools strengthen the societal and industrial integration of SCS. Importantly, all feedback from these channels is systematically recorded and analyzed by UEMI to extract actionable requirements or recommendations. Thus, the methodology creates a robust evidence base to steer both technical design (e.g. component requirements, control algorithms) and non-technical aspects (business models, standardization, policy input).

6 Stakeholder Mapping

6.1 Target Groups

At the proposal stage, SmartCorners performed a stakeholder analysis to identify all the major groups that would influence or be impacted by the project. Already in the early project documentation, the following core stakeholder groups were defined:

- **End Users:** This includes private drivers, passengers, and fleet operators who ultimately use EVs. End users demand affordable, reliable EVs that seamlessly integrate into daily life or business operations. SmartCorners aims to deliver enhanced EV technologies for end-users (e.g. lower cost, increased safety and performance). Engaging end users is critical to ensure the vehicle concepts address real needs like comfort, convenience and trust. In SmartCorners, end users are actively involved in shaping solutions – providing insights via surveys and living labs on what they expect from next-gen EVs in terms of driving experience, charging, and so on. Their feedback helps identify pain points in current mobility (for example, lack of charging or maintenance issues) and prioritize user-centric features.
- **Automotive OEMs:** These are vehicle manufacturers who might integrate SCS into their platforms. Both traditional automakers and new EV startups are considered, as the SCS could appeal to agile emerging OEMs for highly customized EV designs. OEMs are strategic partners in innovation – their participation validates technical feasibility, informs integration challenges, and paves the way for eventual commercialization. By working with OEM stakeholders (e.g. through expert interviews or technical workshops), the project illustrates technological advances and gathers input on how SCS can fit into future vehicle architectures. OEM feedback on design requirements, safety standards, and manufacturing constraints ensures the SCS can achieve market readiness.
- **Suppliers and SMEs:** This group encompasses automotive suppliers, engineering firms, and tech developers (often SMEs) that provide components or subsystems – for instance, IWMs, electronic controllers, AI software modules, or suspension components. These stakeholders are innovation drivers who contribute specialized knowledge and can help accelerate the SCS development. SCS heavily relies on close collaboration with such suppliers to ensure each e-corner component is high-quality and manufacturable. Many project partners themselves fall into this category (including SMEs), which strengthens the consortium’s ability to iterate designs quickly. Engaging external suppliers and SME clusters via dissemination events or direct interviews also helps promote the technologies (turning them into “technology ambassadors” in the supply chain). Their feedback is crucial for ensuring **compatibility** and **standardization**, as they often know how new components can interface with existing vehicle platforms and what standards/certifications must be met.
- **Public Transport Operators:** Operators of buses, trams, shuttles and other public transit fleets form a key stakeholder group highlighted during the stakeholder mapping. They are central for testing SCS technologies in shared mobility contexts. A transit agency, for example, could pilot an SCS-equipped electric minibus to assess benefits

like tighter turning radius or easier maintenance. Their operational data (routes, duty cycles) and performance expectations help tailor SCS for high-frequency, heavy-duty use. Engaging public transport operators (through outreach via organizations like UTIP, the International Association of Public Transport) ensures the project addresses public fleet needs such as reliability, efficiency, and accessibility. It also aligns the project with urban mobility goals, since these stakeholders can demonstrate the impact of SCS on reducing emissions and noise in cities.

- **Logistics and Freight Operators:** As e-commerce and urban delivery grow, logistics companies managing van and truck fleets are crucial stakeholders for SmartCorners. The project explicitly includes urban logistics operators in its engagement strategy. These stakeholders provide real-world insights into the **supply chain needs** – for instance, how a delivery EV equipped with SCS might improve last-mile operations or what requirements exist for cargo space and vehicle uptime. By involving logistics operators, SmartCorners can develop solutions that promote more efficient delivery services and enhanced safety (e.g., better maneuverability in tight urban streets). Their input is used to assign potential use cases (like a SCS-enabled delivery van concept) and ensure the technology can be adapted to commercial fleet contexts (e.g., compatibility with fleet management systems, durability under heavy use).
- **Research and Academia:** Universities, research institutes, and R&D centers are engaged both as partners and external collaborators. The research community contributes to system modeling, simulations, and validation of SmartCorners innovations. In turn, SCS provide valuable data and use cases for scientific research – creating a mutual benefit loop. Engaging researchers (e.g. via the EGVA and ERTRAC networks, or through conference presentations and joint workshops) help advance design methods and spread new knowledge beyond the consortium. It also ensures an **open innovation ecosystem**: the project shares high-quality public deliverables and publishes results with open access, encouraging uptake by other researchers. Academic stakeholders often evaluate the project from a future-oriented perspective, helping to “future-proof” solutions and extend impact through follow-up research or training new engineers.
- **Policy Makers and Public Authorities:** Regulatory bodies, city/regional planners, and transportation policy officials form a critical group that can enable or hinder the adoption of SmartCorners innovations. SmartCorners engages policymakers to align its developments with emerging regulations and policy goals (like the EU Green Deal, urban air quality targets, etc.). By interacting with municipal authorities and ministries (for example, via the POLIS network and direct consultations), the project provides technological evidence to inform policymaking and standardization. Policymakers benefit by understanding which new mobility technologies are upcoming (e.g. vehicles with independent corner modules) and how policy or infrastructure might need to adapt. The project’s impact is enhanced by these interactions: **new policies or incentives can be shaped to support SmartCorners technologies** (challenging outdated regulations and promoting enabling ones). Indeed, part of SmartCorners’ mission is to offer recommendations on policies under preparation, ensuring that by the time the technology is ready for market, the regulatory environment will accommodate innovations like steer-by-wire, e-corners, or AI-based vehicle controls.

In summary, policy stakeholders are engaged through briefings, advisory board input, and inclusion in dissemination events so that SmartCorners can both influence and respond to the policy landscape.

These stakeholder groups were initially identified in the Grant Agreement’s Description of Action and refined as the project progressed . Notably, the consortium expanded the mapping to ensure **broad sector coverage**. For example, “urban authorities and public transport operators” were explicitly included under policymakers to capture city-level influences , and “urban logistics operators” were highlighted under the industry group to capture the freight perspective. Table 4 below summarizes the main stakeholder typologies and their roles in the SmartCorners project:

Table 4. Stakeholder Groups and Its Role and Interest in SmartCorners

Stakeholder Group	Role and Interest in SmartCorners
End Users (<i>drivers, passengers, fleet managers</i>)	Ultimate beneficiaries of SmartCorners innovations. Seek affordable, reliable, and safe EVs with improved comfort and functionality. Provide feedback on user needs and usability (e.g. via surveys, living labs) to ensure the EV design is user-centric.
Automotive OEMs (<i>vehicle manufacturers</i>) & Suppliers/SMEs	Technology developers and integrators of SmartCorners components. They are interested in innovative vehicle architectures to enhance their product portfolio. Collaborate on technical requirements, ensuring e-corner systems meet industry standards and can be manufactured at scale. Their input ensures compatibility with existing platforms and identifies commercialization pathways.
Public Transport Operators (<i>transit agencies</i>)	Potential early adopters for piloting SCS-equipped shuttles or buses in public mobility services. Value improved maneuverability, reduced maintenance, and zero-emission operation for fleets. Provide operational data and testbeds to validate solutions in high-frequency use cases.
Logistics/Freight Operators (<i>delivery and transport companies</i>)	Potential adopters of commercial EV fleets interested in reliability, efficiency (e.g. longer range, fast charging), and cargo optimization. Engage with SmartCorners to co-develop use cases like last-mile delivery vans, ensuring the SCS technology addresses fleet management needs (e.g., durability, backward compatibility with fleet systems).
Research & Academia	Contribute advanced methods (e.g., simulation, AI) for SCS development. Use project data for scholarly research, helping validate and improve models. Benefit from open knowledge exchange; in turn, help evaluate societal impacts and recommend improvements (e.g., via independent studies on e-corner efficiency or safety).

Policy <i>(government agencies, city planners, regulators)</i>	Makers <i>(government agencies, city planners, regulators)</i>	Influence the regulatory and infrastructural environment for SmartCorners adoption, interested in how the technology can help meet policy targets (emissions, safety, innovation). Through engagement (policy briefs, consultations), they receive scientific input for informed regulation and standardization. Their support via incentives, updated standards, and urban planning integration is crucial for scaling SCS.
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Based on the project's objectives and use-case development strategy, the following key stakeholder groups have been identified. Table 5 list the stakeholders that has been identified for engagement and consultations:

Table 5. Identified Stakeholder Network for Engagement and Consultation

Stakeholders	
AUTH (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki)	POLIS Network
BMW	Ricardo
Bosch	Rupprecht Consult
Chalmers University of Technology	RWTH Aachen University (IKA)
CRF (Centro Ricerche Fiat)	UITP (International Association of Public Transport)
EGVIA (European Green Vehicles Initiative Association)	UNEP, UN-Habitat
ERTRAC (European Road Transport Research Advisory Council)	United Nations
ERTICO	Valeo
FEHRL (Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories)	VDI/VDE-IT
FIER.net	Volkswagen
Gruber Logistics	Volvo

In mapping stakeholders, the project also identified specific organizations, which need to be targeted for engagement. This includes project partners as well as external stakeholders. For example, notable entities engaged or consulted include automotive industry leaders (e.g. Bosch, Valeo, BMW, Volkswagen, Volvo), research institutes and universities (e.g. RWTH Aachen, Chalmers University of Technology, AUTH Thessaloniki), and influential networks (e.g. ERTICO – the European transport innovation network, POLIS – city and region network, UITP – public transport association, ERTRAC – road transport R&D council, EGVIAfor2Zero – the 2ZERO partnership association). Logistics companies like Gruber Logistics and consultancies have also been identified. By engaging such a wide array of stakeholders, the SmartCorners project ensures it captures perspectives from all corners of the ecosystem – from the United

Nations (reflecting global policy trends) to niche SMEs – thereby enriching the project’s knowledge base and outreach potential.

6.2 Prioritization Logic

Given the broad stakeholder mapping, SmartCorners developed a **prioritization logic** to focus engagement efforts on the most relevant actors at each stage. Stakeholders are prioritized based on their relevance to three core criteria:

- **Design Relevance:** How directly can the stakeholder’s feedback influence the SmartCorners design and development? Stakeholders like OEMs, Tier-1 suppliers, and logistics operators fall into this category. Their insights on technical requirements, integration challenges, or performance needs can immediately shape component development, control algorithms, and vehicle integration. For example, if multiple suppliers indicate a preferred interface standard for the IWM, the project can adapt to ensure compatibility. Thus, those who can provide detailed technical or user requirements are given high priority for early interviews and collaboration.
- **Market Adoption Potential:** Which stakeholders are likely to be the first adopters or promoters of SmartCorners technologies? Here, public transport operators, logistics fleet operators, and certain end-user segments are key. They are prioritized because their willingness to pilot or invest in technology can accelerate real-world validation and create success stories. For instance, a city bus operator ready to test an SCS-equipped bus could demonstrate the concept’s viability to other cities. Therefore, the project focuses efforts (e.g. dedicated workshops, customized demonstrations) on these actors who have a clear pathway to deploy SmartCorners solutions in the market.
- **Policy & Replication Impact:** Stakeholders, who can influence the wider enabling environment or help replicate the solutions at scale. This includes policymakers, standardization bodies, and research organizations. They might not adopt the technology directly, but they can remove barriers or amplify impact. For example, a national transport ministry can create regulations that allow SCS on public roads, or a standards committee can develop guidelines for AI-driven vehicle control – these actions significantly affect SmartCorners’ ability to scale. Likewise, a research organization might lead follow-up projects that extend SmartCorners concepts to new vehicle types. These stakeholders are engaged with priority when the aim is to secure long-term impact (e.g. through policy workshops, inclusion in advisory boards, dissemination of results to standardization forums).

By applying these criteria, SmartCorners ensures that its engagement activities are strategic and effective. All stakeholders are important, but the project allocates effort in proportion to the expected influence on project success and impact. For example, early in the project, design-relevant stakeholders (OEMs, suppliers) might get more attention to nail down technical specs; as the project nears demonstration, adoption partners (fleets, cities) become focal; and throughout, policy impact stakeholders are kept in the loop to pave the way for acceptance. This targeted approach yields results: feedback gathered from high-priority stakeholders has directly supported SmartCorners’ goals, ensuring the innovations under development remain market-fit and future-proof. The project plans to continue structured

engagement (interviews, surveys, Living Labs) with an evolving set of stakeholders, using this prioritization to guide outreach as new needs emerge and new interested parties come to light.

7 Planned Engagement Actions

Under the framework above, SmartCorners has executed several engagement actions to date (M18) and planned further activities. The major components have been survey campaigns, expert interviews, and regional outreach via Mobility Hubs, each feeding into an ongoing feedback loop.

7.1 Survey Campaigns

The project conducted two rounds of online surveys to capture stakeholder perspectives at different stages:

- **First Survey Round (M9, Feb 2025):** Timed with the **RTR Conference 2025** (a prominent EU road transport R&I event), this survey targeted conference participants and the project's extended network. It aimed to gather initial insights on: (a) barriers and enablers to EV and AI-based vehicle technology adoption, (b) perceptions of modular vehicle design, energy efficiency, and user comfort, and (c) views on data sharing, cloud connectivity, and circular economy practices. Despite a limited sample (initial outreach to conference attendees), the responses provided clear signals. **Initial findings** highlighted that **cost and charging infrastructure are top concerns** for stakeholders considering new EV technologies. In other words, the upfront purchase price of EVs and the availability/speed of charging were the most frequently cited adoption barriers. Conversely, stakeholders identified **modularity, predictive maintenance, and backward compatibility as key value drivers** that would encourage adoption. This suggests that if an EV platform equipped with SCS can easily integrate new features (modularity), prevent breakdowns (via AI-based predictive maintenance), and work with existing systems (backward compatibility), stakeholders see it as significantly more attractive. These insights from the first round were immediately communicated to the technical team and used to refine development priorities (for example, emphasizing the modularity aspect in the next design iteration, and ensuring backwards compatibility of the SCS with conventional vehicle architectures).
- **Second Survey Round (M12–M15, Mar–May 2025):** A broader follow-up survey was circulated online to expert communities and stakeholder contacts gathered through the project's dissemination list. Although the sample size remained modest (**32 participants** in total), it comprised a focused group of experts: the majority were based in urban areas across Europe and primarily working in research or technical roles (e.g. researchers, engineers). This lends credibility to the insights as reflecting informed stakeholder expectations. The second survey results reinforced and expanded upon the initial findings. **Cost emerged unambiguously as the #1 barrier** for adopting new EV technologies, with respondents ranking vehicle affordability as their top priority. When asked about technological advancements that would accelerate EV uptake, "lower cost" was the most frequently chosen, followed closely by "fast charging" capability (Figure 3). **Fast charging infrastructure** and reduced **charging time** were repeatedly highlighted as critical enablers for broader EV adoption, second only to **cost factors**. This underscores that stakeholders view **charging speed and convenience on par with purchase price** in importance – a clear mandate for the SmartCorners project to

emphasize technological solutions that can reduce charging needs or integrate fast-charge compatibility.

Survey Page 1 Page 2 Page 3 Page 4

SmartCorners Survey

SmartCorners is an innovative vehicle technology that is designed to advance electric vehicles (EVs) by integrating multiple critical functions such as propulsion, braking, suspension, and steering, into compact, modular systems called “smart corners.” These systems use new advancements like in-wheel motors, AI-driven controls, and predictive maintenance to enhance vehicle efficiency, safety, and user experience.

For further information and a project video visit <https://smartcorners.eu/> or <https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartcorners/>

Through this survey, we aim to gather valuable insights from stakeholders to better understand the challenges, opportunities, and expectations for implementing advanced vehicle technologies like SmartCorners. Your input will help shaping the future of mobility. **Thank you for your time and efforts to answering the questions—we highly appreciate it!**

Privacy Policy for the SmartCorners Survey *

We are committed to protect your privacy in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This survey collects anonymous data to gather insights on SmartCorners technology for research and development purposes. No personally identifiable information will be collected, and all responses will be stored securely and analyzed collectively.

By ticking the box below, you confirm that you have read and understood this privacy policy and agree to the anonymous processing of your responses.

I agree to the data protection notice and consent to the anonymous processing of my responses.

Figure 2. SmartCorners Survey Form

Concerns over AI implementation focused primarily on data security, reinforcing the need for clear regulatory frameworks and transparent governance structures. Additionally, energy and emission reduction are perceived as extremely important for fleet management and operations.

Design related insights confirmed that modularity and compact vehicle architecture are viewed as essential for improving both operational and environmental performance. Participants rated predictive maintenance and driving comfort as very important feature, while AI-enabled adaptive safety features as moderately important. Backward compatibility was emphasized as a very important factor, particularly for fleet management contexts.

The survey highlighted strong support for sustainability principles. Participants emphasized the need for recyclable materials, efficient recycling systems, and circular design concepts. Public transport systems were perceived as insufficient in many urban settings, with calls for better coverage, improved reliability, and greater accessibility. Furthermore, the lack of supporting infrastructure, particularly charging stations and integrated digital systems, was seen as a major barrier to the effective deployment of new vehicle technologies.

Regarding cloud-based solutions, participants expressed cautious optimism. Many acknowledged the benefits of cloud data sharing for improving traffic efficiency, maintenance

operations, and predictive analytics. However, they also stressed the importance of privacy protection, transparency, and user control. The need for regulatory oversight and clear public communication was viewed as critical for building trust in such systems.

In terms of policy measures, respondents recommended a mix of financial and non-financial incentives to accelerate the adoption of smart vehicle technologies. Financial measures included tax relief, subsidies, and reduced costs for public charging or services. Non-financial incentives included priority lane access and dedicated infrastructure. Participants also suggested for greater public-private cooperation, awareness campaigns, and education programs. Specific policy gaps identified included the lack of regulation for AI, insufficient consumer protections, and limited support for local production and supply chains in emerging markets.

As illustrated in Figure 3 (a–c), vehicle cost emerges as a key factor in stakeholders’ EV adoption decisions. The survey results also highlight the importance of energy efficiency in fleet operations and strong support for sustainable materials, modular design, and recycling systems in automotive manufacturing.

Figure 3a. Key factors influencing EV technology adoption

Figure 3b. Importance of energy efficiency and emissions

Figure 3c. Recyclability strategies in manufacturing

Figure 3. Survey Results on EV Adoption Factors, Sustainability Priorities, and Operational Considerations

All survey findings have been documented and analyzed. Importantly, these gained insights are not just reported – they have been acted upon. The consortium **updated its policy brief** and internal design requirements based on the survey results. For instance, seeing cost and charging as dominant factors, led to investigations on how SCS could enable cost reductions (e.g., by simplifying vehicle assembly or maintenance) and how to facilitate faster charging (perhaps through energy-efficient designs that extend range per charge). The emphasis on data security has led the team to prioritize robust cybersecurity measures in the vehicle’s cloud connectivity architecture. Additionally, the strong call for circularity is influencing the selection of materials and the plan for end-of-life reuse of components (tying into the project’s sustainability work). In summary, the surveys provided quantitative evidence to steer the project in alignment with stakeholder expectations, and this evidence has already informed project deliverables and development plans.

7.2 Expert Interviews

Alongside surveys, expert interviews are conducted to gain deeper qualitative insights. These interviews are semi-structured dialogues with individuals or small groups who represent the key stakeholder categories identified earlier. The interview campaign is **ongoing (rolling)**, meaning interviews are scheduled throughout the project as needed rather than all at once. This allows the project to continuously validate assumptions and gather feedback at different milestones. By M18, the consortium has engaged experts such as automotive R&D managers from OEMs and suppliers, public transit authority officials, EV infrastructure providers, and policy advisors in sustainable mobility.

The goals of the expert interviews are to: (1) **validate use cases and requirements** developed within SmartCorners, and (2) **collect detailed feedback and ideas** that might not surface in surveys. For example, an expert interview with a **city mobility planner** provided insights into how a compact, maneuverable SCS-equipped vehicle could help in traffic-calmed urban centers but also raised questions about regulatory approval for four-wheel-steering vehicles on public roads. This kind of detailed exchange helps SmartCorners address specific real-world challenges. Likewise, discussions with a **logistics fleet manager** validated the importance of backward compatibility – the manager highlighted that any new electric van must be

serviceable within their existing maintenance operations, otherwise downtime costs would be prohibitive. This directly reinforced the survey finding on backward compatibility, but with richer context (e.g., what kinds of compatibility – parts, software, diagnostics – matter most to fleet operators).

Another area explored in the interviews is **market scalability and business models**. The project spoke with an **EV leasing company expert**, who stressed that total cost of ownership over 5-7 years is the key metric for fleet adoption. Through that interview, the project gleaned that features like predictive maintenance (reducing breakdowns) could significantly improve uptime and thus economic viability, which became a stronger selling point in SmartCorners' exploitation considerations. Interviews with **technical experts** (such as automotive engineers not in the project) also serve as peer-review of SmartCorners' technical approach – for instance, a vehicle dynamics professor was interviewed to evaluate the project's assumptions on improved ride comfort from active suspension. Such interviews validate the scientific and engineering soundness of the proposed innovations.

All interviews are documented in minutes and thematic summaries. The qualitative feedback is coded and fed into the project's internal requirements tracker. Recurring themes or critical comments from interviews are used to update the design. For example, when multiple experts highlighted **functional safety** concerns (ensuring fail-safe behavior of SCS including e.g. steer-by-wire), the project responded by allocating additional effort to the safety analysis and fault tolerance design in WP2. This is a direct outcome of stakeholder engagement, making the technology more robust.

The expert interviews have provided in-depth, contextual intelligence that complements the broader trends seen in the surveys. They verify that SmartCorners' envisioned use cases (from autonomous shuttles to modular passenger cars) are relevant and desirable, while also pinpointing what conditions must be met for success (cost thresholds, regulatory approvals, user acceptance factors). The interview program will continue through the project's second half, targeting new experts (e.g., standardization committee members, additional city partners) as the focus shifts towards demonstration and deployment. These dialogues ensure **continuous validation** of SmartCorners' approach by the very experts and decision-makers who will influence its real-world adoption.

7.3 Regional Outreach and Engagement via Mobility Hubs

SmartCorners recognizes that bringing stakeholders **hands-on experience** with its innovations greatly enhances engagement. To this end, the project leverages **UEMI's Mobility Hubs** as regional outreach platforms. The Mobility Hubs are essentially living labs or demonstration sites in various cities where sustainable mobility solutions are showcased and co-developed with local stakeholders. Through Task 7.2, SmartCorners planned a series of outreach and co-creation sessions at these hubs, with the dual aim of disseminating project concepts and gathering localised feedback.

In the first 18 months, preparatory steps for Mobility Hub workshops have been undertaken. Locations in partner cities (e.g., in Germany and Italy) were identified where an initial concept showcase can be held once a SCS prototype or simulation is available. Regional stakeholders

– such as city authorities, public transport companies, local logistics firms, civic groups, and academia – are invited to these sessions. The idea is to simulate or demonstrate components of the SCS (for example, a virtual reality demonstration of a SCS-equipped vehicle navigating tight urban streets, or a physical demo) and then facilitate an interactive discussion/workshop around it.

This **co-creative regional engagement** allows stakeholders to contextualize SmartCorners innovative technology in their own city or operation. For instance, a Mobility Hub workshop in a dense historic city might explore how ultra-steerable SCS-equipped vehicles could solve last-mile delivery in narrow alleys, whereas a workshop in a suburban area might focus on using SCS-equipped EVs to enhance first-mile/last-mile connectivity to transit stations. Stakeholders on-site can offer insights such as “in our city, parking space is a huge issue – a vehicle that can maneuver or even move sideways would be extremely valuable,” or conversely, “maintenance facilities here are limited, so any new EV tech must be highly reliable or have remote diagnostics.” Such inputs are extremely valuable for the project’s replication and deployment strategies (WP6).

Moreover, these outreach events double **capacity building**. They raise awareness among local decision-makers about cutting-edge EV technologies, potentially spurring interest in future pilot projects. SmartCorners has coordinated with related EU initiatives (through the 2ZERO partnership and the E-VOLVE Cluster) to piggyback on events and ensure a good turnout of interested stakeholders at Mobility Hub sessions. For example, an upcoming plan is to present SmartCorners at a regional sustainable mobility forum co-organized by the POLIS network, which will attract city officials from across Europe.

Though the full rollout of Mobility Hub events was in early stages by M18 (partly due to aligning with prototype readiness), the strategy is clear: **engage stakeholders in their home environment**. This grounds the feedback in practical reality and often elicits very concrete suggestions (or offers to collaborate). As these workshops progress, results (feedback, ideas, potential pilot leads) will be documented. One expected outcome is the identification of at least 2-3 candidate cities or operators interested in serving as hosts for SmartCorners’ demonstration vehicles in later project stages. Indeed, early conversations have already begun with one public transport operator who, after a regional outreach discussion, expressed interest in testing theSCS on one of their electric mini-buses.

The regional outreach via Mobility Hubs represents the **local, practical dimension** of SmartCorners’ stakeholder engagement. It ensures that beyond surveys and expert interviews, the project also listens to and works with the people who would implement and use its innovations on the ground. This approach also aids **replication**, as it plants seeds in various locales that could adopt the SCS post-project. As the project moves forward, these engagements will intensify, creating a pipeline from lab to real-life deployment via direct stakeholder collaboration in the field.

8 Assessment and Reporting

Assessment and reporting processes are central to ensuring that stakeholder engagement activities in SmartCorners are effective, actionable, and capable of shaping project outcomes. UEMI, as the leader of dissemination and engagement (WP7), is responsible for systematically evaluating the feedback received from surveys, interviews, and workshops, and ensuring that these insights are integrated into relevant WPs, particularly those focused on replication, policy alignment, and user-centric design.

8.1 Continuous Assessment and Reporting

To ensure that all engagement activity actually translates into project improvements, SmartCorners put in place a clear **assessment and reporting process**. The process works as follows:

- After each major engagement (survey round, interview, workshop), the **results are compiled in an internal report or summary**. Quantitative data (survey statistics) and qualitative input (notable quotes, suggestions) are analyzed by the team. For example, after the first survey, UEMI produced a summary report highlighting the top-ranked factors (cost, charging) and key qualitative comments.
- These findings are then **mapped to the relevant WPs and Key Exploitable Results**. A feedback matrix is used internally: each point of feedback is linked to whether it affects vehicle hardware design (WP2), control algorithms (WP3), use case definitions (WP1), business models (WP7 exploitation), etc. For instance, “stakeholders want predictive maintenance” was mapped to WP3 (controls development) and WP5 (digital architecture for cloud diagnostics), to ensure those WPs incorporate this requirement. Similarly, “data security concern” was mapped to WP5 (cloud/data) and WP7 (to address dissemination and policy outreach).
- The **consortium discusses these inputs at technical coordination meetings**. Where needed, actions are assigned. A concrete example: the concern about AI and data privacy noted in the second survey was brought to a consortium meeting, resulting in the action “Define data governance and privacy approach in deliverable D5.x and include a section on how the AI algorithms handle data securely.” This action came directly from stakeholder feedback and is tracked to completion.
- Progress on integrating feedback is documented in this deliverable and will be updated in the subsequent engagement report (deliverable D7.4 due to M36). Essentially, **traceability of stakeholder feedback** is maintained: the project can show how a comment or suggestion led to a change or consideration in the project. This is important not only for internal management, but also to report back to stakeholders (“you said, we did”) thereby building trust. In fact, the **SmartCorners policy brief** was updated after the second survey round, which is a tangible output demonstrating responsiveness to feedback (it now includes, for example, a greater emphasis on recommendations for charging infrastructure and data policy, as prompted by the survey insights).

To quantify the project's societal progress, SmartCorners also considers SRLs. At project start, the SRL of many SmartCorners innovations was relatively low – since they were largely at concept stage, societal readiness (awareness, willingness to adopt) was limited. Through engagement activities, the project aims to raise the SRL by addressing existing gaps (for instance, lack of user awareness or policy frameworks). By M18, there are signs of SRL improvement: stakeholders in our network have moved from unfamiliarity with SCS to actively discussing how to implement them, indicating a shift from SRL 2-3 (“society has minimal awareness”) towards SRL 4-5 (“engagement with early adopters and communities”). We will continue measuring this qualitatively (e.g., via follow-up questions in surveys like “How likely would you be to support an initiative to test SCS-equipped vehicles in your city?”). A higher SRL by project end would mean SmartCorners solutions are broadly seen as acceptable and desirable, smoothing the path for commercialization.

Assessment and reporting in SmartCorners is not a one-time task, but an ongoing cycle that mirrors the engagement loop. By continuously funneling stakeholder inputs into the project's work streams and documenting the outcomes, the project ensures that engagement is effective and actionable. The ultimate measure of success will be if stakeholder-driven adjustments lead to a final SCS that is truly fit-for-purpose and supported by its end-users and ecosystem. All indications thus far suggest the project is on the right track – course corrections have been made when needed, and stakeholder excitement is building as they see their input reflected in the project outputs.

8.2 Feedback Integration into Project Outcomes

Several concrete examples illustrate how stakeholder feedback has been integrated:

- **Technical Requirements:** The deliverable on technical requirements (D1.2) included an analysis of how each requirement maps to stakeholder needs. For instance, a requirement for **sensorized suspension arms** was linked to Tier-1 suppliers and research institutions as targeted users, with the benefit of enabling new AI methods for them. This mapping was informed by early stakeholder discussions indicating suppliers and researchers are keen on innovations that allow for new control strategies. By explicitly connecting requirements to stakeholder groups, the project ensured that design choices stayed aligned with those groups' expectations.
- **Design of SCS:** Input from vehicle manufacturers and component suppliers stressed **standardization and compatibility**. In response, the SCS' physical design was adjusted to conform to certain interface standards (for mounting, communication protocols) that were not originally in the concept but were raised during engagement. This will make it easier for an OEM or retrofitter to adopt the SCS without needing bespoke adapters, addressing a potential adoption hurdle. Similarly, feedback about maintenance from fleet operators influenced the **modularity of the design** – the team decided to make the corner units more easily swappable in case of failure, as fleet stakeholders favored quick replacement over complex repair in the field.
- **AI and Control Features:** The strong interest in **predictive maintenance** from stakeholders caused the project to prioritize development of structural health

monitoring algorithms (e.g. for the composite suspension components). The original plan had this as a lower priority, but engagement demonstrated it is a key selling point, so resources were reallocated to ensure a reliable predictive maintenance feature is delivered (with a target of >95% fault prediction success according to the project KPIs). In parallel, concerns about AI safety and transparency led the project to plan a user-oriented explanation feature – for example, a simple interface that shows the driver or fleet manager what the AI is doing or any actions it’s taking (to build trust). This idea was not in the initial proposal but emerged from stakeholder dialogues about transparency.

- **Use Case Refinement:** Initially, the project considered a broad set of use cases (private cars, robo-taxis, delivery vans, buses, etc.). Engagement results helped **narrow and prioritize** these. Given the enthusiastic response from public transport and delivery sectors, SmartCorners is focusing on a **last-mile delivery van** use case and an **urban shuttle** use case as primary demonstrators. End users (through surveys) showed moderate interest in advanced driving features for private cars, whereas commercial stakeholders strongly valued practical benefits like maneuverability and uptime. Thus, the project’s demonstration strategy shifted more towards business-to-business/business-to-government use cases (business/government fleets) where impact could be higher initially, which aligns with stakeholder readiness to participate in pilots. Of course, the modular SCS still applies to private cars, but the pathway to the market might start with fleet applications.
- **Policy and Standardization Inputs:** Through its engagement with networks like ERTRAC and EGVA (via the LeMesurier project’s activities), SmartCorners is contributing to broader 2ZERO partnership discussions. Feedback from policy stakeholders – such as the **need for clear regulatory guidelines for AI in vehicles and standards for interoperability** – has been captured in SmartCorners’ policy brief and communications. The project has, for example, proposed in its dissemination materials a recommendation for **new EU standards on modular EV architectures**, which was directly motivated by stakeholder dialogues pointing out that current vehicle type-approval regulations don’t envision vehicles with swappable corners or extreme steering angles. By offering such scientific input to regulation and standardization efforts, SmartCorners not only integrates feedback into its own work but also feeds it upward into the policy environment, amplifying the entire project impact.

Overall, the integration of feedback is an area where SmartCorners excels – it embodies the ethos of a user-centric design project. Every significant piece of stakeholder input is seen as an opportunity to improve the project outcomes, whether that’s a tweak to a technical design or a new emphasis on exploitation plans. This responsiveness has been recognized by stakeholders themselves; some interviewees noted that they were impressed to see their suggestions reflected in later project updates. Such positive reinforcement encourages continued engagement and sets the stage for a supportive community around SmartCorners as it heads towards implementation.

9 Alignment with 2ZERO Objectives and Impact Pathways

SmartCorners is funded under Horizon Europe HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01-01 and reporting on the results of the co-programmed 2ZERO partnership, and as such, it contributes to the broader **Strategic and Specific Objectives** of 2ZERO, as well as the **Operational Objectives** that the partnership strives for. The stakeholder engagement activities and technological innovations of SmartCorners are mapped to these goals, ensuring maximum impact. Below we detail how SmartCorners aligns with the key 2ZERO objectives:

- **Strategic Objective: Climate-Neutral Mobility & Air Quality.** The overarching aim of 2ZERO is to achieve a climate-neutral and clean road transport system by 2050, including improved air quality. SmartCorners contributes directly to this by focusing on **zero tailpipe emission** EV architectures. By improving the appeal and performance of EVs (through enhanced efficiency and user-centric features), SmartCorners accelerates the transition away from internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles. For example, SmartCorners' innovations related to the IWM and its control strategies target a >20% improvement in real-world energy efficiency (range), which not only reduces greenhouse gas emissions but also makes EVs more practical for users (thus encouraging EV uptake). Additionally, the project's emphasis on reducing vehicle weight and optimizing powertrain components contributes to efficiency gains that align with climate goals. The **improved energy efficiency and emissions reduction of SCS-equipped vehicles** were recognized as "extremely important" by stakeholders for fleet operations, reinforcing that our technical approach resonates with the climate objective of 2ZERO.
- **Specific Objective: Develop affordable, user-centric EV solutions across Europe.** 2ZERO explicitly aims to **develop zero-tailpipe, affordable user-centric solutions** and accelerate their acceptance. SmartCorners is fundamentally a **user-centric EV design project** – "User-centred Optimal Design [...]" is in its title. It addresses affordability by targeting significant cost reductions: the project has set quantitative KPIs for cost, such as a **5–10% reduction in overall EV cost** through its modular e-corner approach, named SCS. This is achieved by design innovations (e.g. simplifying chassis and integrating functions to reduce part count) and by reducing development time (SmartCorners aims for >30% reduction in EV system development time, which can lower R&D costs and ultimately consumer prices). These figures directly support the 2ZERO goal of making EVs affordable. On the user-centric side, SmartCorners increases interior space (cabin volume +15%, luggage +20% in concept) and improves comfort and handling, addressing user needs for practicality and comfort. The strong stakeholder feedback on cost and comfort validates that SmartCorners is aligned with what users want, thus increasing acceptance. By involving endusers in design, SmartCorners also accelerates acceptance – people are more likely to accept solutions they had a hand in shaping. This co-creation aspect embodies the 2ZERO objective of user-centric development.
- **Specific Objective: Reduce non-powertrain emissions and noise.** 2ZERO includes reducing **non-tailpipe emissions (like brake/tyre particles) and traffic noise** in its objectives. SmartCorners contributes here in multiple ways. Its **in-wheel motor with**

regenerative braking capability can recuperate more braking energy (project target: +9% braking energy recovery), meaning less reliance on friction brakes – this can reduce brake pad particulate emissions, a non-exhaust pollutant. Also, by actively controlling wheel movement (camber, toe) and suspension, SmartCorners can reduce tire scrub and potentially prolong tire life, indirectly cutting tyre particle emissions. Regarding noise, active suspension and smoother electric drivetrain can reduce vehicle noise, especially important in urban settings for improving quality of life. While SmartCorners has not yet quantified noise reduction, its design (electric drive, optimized contact with road) inherently produces less noise than conventional ICE vehicles, supporting 2ZERO’s noise reduction aim. Furthermore, stakeholder engagement indicates city stakeholders value these aspects – quieter, cleaner operation was cited as a benefit when discussing use cases for public transport integration.

- **Specific Objective: Develop user-friendly charging infrastructure concepts (vehicle-grid interaction).** This is a 2ZERO goal where SmartCorners is a more indirect contributor, as the project itself is not developing charging infrastructure. However, through stakeholder surveys we identified “fast charging & lower cost” as top priorities to accelerate EV uptake. SmartCorners responds by considering how its design can **minimize charging needs** (via efficiency and possibly battery-swapping concepts due to modularity) and by ensuring compatibility with existing charging standards (backward compatibility again). Additionally, by engaging with infrastructure stakeholders in our outreach, SmartCorners feeds into the broader conversation on charging solutions. For example, if a public transport operator stakeholder is interested in a SCS-equipped bus, we simultaneously discuss depot charging or opportunity charging needs for that bus – these insights can inform other projects or policies focused on charging. In essence, SmartCorners stays aligned by ensuring its vehicle does not create new burdens for infrastructure and by highlighting infrastructure needs in its dissemination (thus guiding 2ZERO efforts on infrastructure).
- **Specific Objective: Demonstrate innovative use cases integrating zero-emission vehicles and infrastructure.** 2ZERO wants projects to **demonstrate innovative use cases for zero-emission vehicles in mobility of people and goods**. SmartCorners is planning exactly this: by the end of the project, the goal is to have prototype demonstrations of its SCS-equipped EV platform in relevant use cases (e.g., a last-mile delivery van scenario, an autonomous urban shuttle scenario). Through the stakeholder engagement detailed above, we have identified and refined high-impact use cases – for instance, a modular **last-mile delivery vehicle** that can reduce emissions in urban logistics, or a **shared autonomous shuttle** for first/last-mile connections in cities. These align with 2ZERO’s vision of new mobility solutions. The project is preparing for demonstration by engaging early with the stakeholders who would host or operate these pilots, ensuring that when we showcase the technology, it will be in a realistic operational context (not just a lab). By doing so, SmartCorners contributes to 2ZERO not only through technical R&I, but through tangible demonstrations of how zero-emission vehicles can be integrated into real transport systems for people (public transport, shuttles) and goods (urban logistics).

- **Specific Objective: Support life-cycle analysis and circular economy.** Another 2ZERO objective is to embed circular economy thinking – developing tools and skills for effective design and deployment in a circular context. SmartCorners, through its design and stakeholder input, supports this objective. The project uses **lightweight composite materials** and designs components for durability and modular replacement, which contributes to longer vehicle lifetime and easier refurbishing (a circular economy strategy). Stakeholders’ focus on recyclability and sustainable materials has reinforced our commitment to these principles. We plan to assess the life-cycle impact of the SCS (for example, does the reduction in component count and increased energy efficiency offset the impact of any advanced materials used?). Moreover, by advocating for backward compatibility and upgradability, SmartCorners promotes reuse – an operator could upgrade an old EV with SCS instead of buying a whole new vehicle, potentially reducing waste. These align well with 2ZERO’s circular economy goals, as do our dissemination findings: we share data openly, which can feed into life-cycle analysis research by others.

On the **Operational Objectives and KPIs** side (the more quantifiable metrics 2ZERO tracks), SmartCorners is contributing in several ways:

- **Broad stakeholder coverage:** The 2ZERO partnership aims to involve a broad range of stakeholders across sectors. SmartCorners exemplifies this by engaging stakeholders from automotive industry, academia, small businesses, cities, and international bodies – as detailed, SmartCorners has addressed OEMs, SMEs, researchers, public operators, etc. with the engagement actions. This broad coverage is one of 2ZERO’s KPIs, and our project is often highlighted (via the LeMesurier CSA) as a project doing well in stakeholder breadth.
- **SME participation:** 2ZERO tracks the number of SMEs involved in projects. SmartCorners includes multiple SME partners in its project consortium (e.g., HER, BLW, AIG) and engages additional SMEs externally (through supplier outreach and events). By ensuring SMEs are both contributing to and benefiting from the project, we hit the KPI for SME involvement. For instance, SMEs in SmartCorners are leading or co-leading work on niche areas like advanced suspension design and cloud services, strengthening innovation capacity.
- **Standardization support:** An operational objective is to support standardization. SmartCorners contributes by sharing results with standardization bodies and aligning with existing standards. We have connections to groups like the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) and United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) working on vehicle safety standards through our partners. Any data or experiences relevant to standards (such as safety performance of steer-by-wire) are reported in our deliverables and via liaison. Moreover, we identified a gap in standards for certain e-corner functions and have raised this in 2ZERO forums, which may lead to future standardization work. By engaging stakeholders like ERTICO and ERTRAC, we ensure the project’s knowledge feeds into the standardization roadmap.
- **Innovation dissemination (publications, patents):** 2ZERO tracks the number of publications and patents from projects. SmartCorners is on track here: we have

planned scientific publications (the first technical paper is in preparation using results from WP2/WP3 to be submitted to a 2025 conference). The dissemination plan (D7.1) targets >5 scientific publications during the project, contributing to the KPI of knowledge dissemination. On patents, the project partners are considering intellectual property (IP) protection for certain inventions (e.g., a novel suspension actuator design) – at least one patent application is expected, which would directly tick the “number of patent applications” KPI for 2ZERO. Additionally, by producing open access deliverables and communicating this information in events, we ensure wide dissemination of results, aligning with the objective of ensuring broad outreach.

- Scientific input for regulation:** 2ZERO wants projects to inform policy and regulation. Through stakeholder engagement and the resulting policy recommendations, SmartCorners provides such input. Our policy brief distills what we learned (e.g., the need for AI regulation and consumer protection in smart mobility, the importance of incentives for EV adoption) and shares it with policymakers. The SmartCorners findings are integrated into the **LeMesurier project’s KPI framework**, which will aggregate impact across projects for the European Commission (EC) – SmartCorners data on things like energy efficiency improvements, user acceptance levels, etc., are being used to quantify progress towards climate and mobility targets. By doing this, we directly contribute to the evaluation of the 2ZERO partnership’s effectiveness and help steer future policy (LeMesurier will recommend measurement and evaluation improvements for 2ZERO based on project data).

In Table 6 below, a few key alignments between 2ZERO’s objectives and SmartCorners’ contributions are summarized:

Table 6. Summary of 2ZERO’s Objective or KPI and SmartCorners Contribution

2ZERO Objective or KPI	SmartCorners Contribution
Affordable, user-centric EV solutions <i>(Specific Obj.)</i>	Modular SCS architecture reduces EV cost by an estimated 5–10%, making EVs more affordable. User-centric design improves space (cabin +15%) and comfort, enhancing acceptance. Continuous user engagement ensures the solution meets customer needs, accelerating acceptance across Europe.
Reduce non-exhaust emissions & noise <i>(Specific Obj.)</i>	Regenerative braking and lightweight design: +9% braking energy recovery reduces brake use (less brake dust). Active control can diminish tire wear and vehicle noise. IWMs eliminate engine noise and local emissions, directly improving urban air quality and noise levels.
Demonstrate innovative use cases <i>(Specific Obj.)</i>	Working with transport and logistics stakeholders to pilot SCS-equipped EVs in real-world scenarios (e.g., autonomous shuttles, e-delivery vans). These demonstrations show how zero-emission vehicles with SmartCorners technology integrate with infrastructure (e.g., smart charging depots) for people & goods mobility, providing practical case studies for 2ZERO’s mission.

<p>Life-cycle & Circularity (Specific Obj.)</p>	<p>Emphasis on sustainable materials and modular design: using durable composites and designing SCS for easy replacement/upgrades prolongs vehicle life. Stakeholders rated recyclability and modularity as critical, and SmartCorners incorporates these by enabling component reuse and upgrade (backward compatibility means current fleets can be retrofitted, reducing waste). This supports circular economy objectives.</p>
<p>Broad stakeholder coverage (Operational Obj.)</p>	<p>Engaged diverse sectors: automotive OEMs & suppliers, SMEs, city authorities, academia, transport operators. SmartCorners' stakeholder list spans public, private, academic, and civil society actors, fulfilling the breadth intended by 2ZERO.</p>
<p>Involvement of SMEs (Operational Obj.)</p>	<p>Consortium includes SMEs as core partners (driving innovation in their niches). Additional SMEs reached via outreach (e.g., local tech startups via Mobility Hubs). This ensures smaller actors benefit from and contribute to the project, aligning with 2ZERO's SME participation metric.</p>
<p>Support to standardization & regulation (Operational Obj.)</p>	<p>Providing scientific input to policy: SmartCorners outputs (e.g., recommendations on AI vehicle safety, data governance) are shared with regulatory stakeholders. Partners in SmartCorners participate in standardization working groups and relay project findings (for example, data from our safety tests can inform future EV safety standards). We actively disseminate results to bodies like ERTRAC and the EC, aiding informed regulation development.</p>
<p>Wide dissemination & publications (Operational Obj.)</p>	<p>Extensive dissemination plan: participating in conferences (e.g., RTR 2025), publishing open access papers (first paper expected in 2025), and maintaining public communication (website, LinkedIn). By M18, SmartCorners has presented at least 2 major events and prepared multiple publications, directly contributing to the KPIs on dissemination. SmartCorners deliverables with dissemination level public and the engagement itself (surveys, etc.) also act as dissemination tools to spread knowledge.</p>

Through the LeMesurier project (the 2ZERO CSA on KPI measurement), SmartCorners has reported its expected impacts which feed into the **2ZERO Partnership KPI framework**. This ensures a transparent mapping of how each technical achievement (like % energy efficiency gain, % cost reduction, etc.) translates to partnership-level goals (e.g., CO2 reduction potential, increased market share of EVs). For example, SmartCorners' >20% range improvement can contribute to reducing range anxiety, hence increasing EV uptake, which is quantified under 2ZERO KPIs for market penetration. Similarly, our engagement-driven approach contributes to KPIs around **social acceptance** (often measured via surveys of willingness to adopt EVs – an area where our project actually generates data).

SmartCorners is not an isolated project; it is an integral part of the 2ZERO partnership roadmap. By validating its innovations with stakeholders, SmartCorners increases the likelihood that its outcomes will directly support 2ZERO's mission of zero-emission, **user-**

centric mobility solutions. The project's contributions to cost reduction, energy efficiency, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge dissemination all serve the **impact pathways** envisioned by 2ZERO – from technology development to market deployment and policy integration. As the project progresses, it will continue to orient its activities (including future demonstrations and exploitation plans) to maximize alignment with these strategic objectives, ensuring that SmartCorners leaves a legacy not only in its own prototypes, but also in advancing Europe's journey to clean and smart mobility.

10 Summary and Outlook

Deliverable D7.3 has detailed how the SmartCorners project actively engaged a wide spectrum of stakeholders and domain experts to validate and enhance its technological and user-centric innovations. By implementing a structured engagement strategy – underpinned by the **four-step loop** of **Identify, Co-create, Evaluate, Adapt** – the project has ensured that feedback from endusers, industry, and public authorities continually informs the design and development of the SmartCorners system. We demonstrated that **cost, charging infrastructure, and reliability** are paramount concerns for stakeholders adopting new EV technologies, and that features like **modularity, backward compatibility, and predictive maintenance** are seen as key enablers of adoption. These insights, gathered through surveys and interviews, were not only documented but have been integrated into the project’s technical work (e.g., emphasizing cost reduction and maintenance features) and its outreach (e.g., policy recommendations for charging and data governance).

SmartCorners’ stakeholder mapping encompassed everyone from **public transport operators and logistics companies** (who will operate the vehicles), to **OEMs and suppliers** (who will build them), to **researchers and policymakers** (who will influence the ecosystem in which they operate). By prioritizing stakeholders who have the most influence on design, early adoption, and regulatory acceptance, the project made efficient use of engagement opportunities – focusing efforts where they yield the greatest impact. Concretely, the project has cultivated a stakeholder community that includes major industry players and innovative SMEs, city networks and European platforms, ensuring SmartCorners is positioned within a supportive innovation ecosystem. This community-oriented approach has already led to valuable partnerships, such as interest from a city to pilot the SCS technology and input to EU-wide discussions on EV standards.

The engagement actions described – online surveys, expert interviews, and local Living Lab workshops – form a **continuous feedback loop** that strengthened SmartCorners’ outcomes. The first half of the project benefited greatly from these actions: they validated the project’s initial directions and uncovered new considerations (like the emphasis on data security and circular design) that might otherwise have been overlooked. By M18, these efforts have increased the **SRL** of SmartCorners solutions, with key stakeholders not only aware of the project but actively contributing to its refinement. This sets the stage for a smoother path in the second half of the project when prototypes and demonstrations will come to the fore.

Looking ahead, the **outlook for SmartCorners’ engagement** is very positive. In the next project phase, we plan to:

- **Deepen Engagement for Demonstrations:** As the technical WPs deliver prototypes (e.g., a functioning SCS), we will organize demonstration events and hands-on sessions with stakeholders. Potential pilot implementations with selected operators (those identified through our engagement so far) will be a focus. This will serve as a real-world test of both technology and user acceptance. We anticipate learning even more once stakeholders can physically interact with SCS-equipped vehicles.
- **Expanding the Stakeholder Network:** Through continued dissemination (conferences, publications) and leveraging the 2ZERO partnership channels, we aim to bring additional stakeholders into the conversation. For instance, as we publish our results,

we expect more cities or companies to approach us with interest. We will use the remaining time to onboard such new stakeholders, possibly conducting a third survey or additional interviews to capture any new perspectives (especially as the external environment for EVs is rapidly evolving with new policies and market developments in 2025/2026).

- **Iterate and Finalize Exploitation Strategy:** All the feedback on drivers and barriers will crystallize into the project's exploitation and business plans (to be reported in the deliverable D7.4 and D8.x). The engagement will ensure that SmartCorners' exploitation strategy is grounded in reality – identifying the correct entry markets, the needed partnerships, and go-to-market business models that make sense. For example, if stakeholders consistently indicate that retrofitting existing fleets is a viable path, our exploitation might pivot to offering SCS as a retrofit kit, whereas if OEM integration seems more promising, we'll strategize accordingly. The **stakeholder-driven KPI alignment** we performed with LeMesurier will also guide us in setting post-project targets (like how many cities or fleets are to be involved in follow-up pilots).
- **Monitor and Maximize Impact on 2ZERO Goals:** In the concluding period, we will closely monitor how SmartCorners is contributing to 2ZERO's impact pathways and adjust actions to maximize this. For instance, if an opportunity arises to contribute data or testimony to a policy hearing on EV standards, we will take it (thus influencing regulation, a 2ZERO operational objective). We will also document our contributions to environmental and socio-economic impacts (e.g., potential CO2 savings if SmartCorners technology is widely adopted) to demonstrate alignment with 2ZERO's high-level goals.

The stakeholder engagement detailed in this report has been invaluable in **de-risking and strengthening** the SmartCorners project. It ensured the project did not develop technology in a vacuum, but rather in constant consultation with the community it aims to serve. This not only increases the chances of successful adoption of the SCS in the market but also contributes to the broader mission of making European road transport more sustainable, innovative, and user-friendly. By actively involving stakeholders, SmartCorners exemplifies a user-centric innovation approach – one that others in the 2ZERO partnership can emulate for collective success. The project will carry this momentum forward, continuing the conversation with stakeholders up to and beyond the project's end, thereby turning the SmartCorners vision into a reality that is endorsed and embraced by its end users.

The next deliverable (D7.4) will provide an updated report on dissemination, communication & engagement, capturing the outcomes of the actions outlined in this report, the deliverable D7.2 entitled "Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan (2)," and any new strategies deployed. We anticipate that by then, we will be reporting not just on plans and intermediate feedback, but on concrete deployment experiences and stakeholder testimonials from pilot implementations. **SmartCorners' engagement journey is ongoing**, but the foundation laid in the deliverables D7.3 and D7.2 assures that the project's innovations will be well-aligned with user needs and market conditions, maximizing impact and paving the way for successful exploitation in the project's 2nd reporting period.

11 Conclusion

The evidence collected during the first reporting period confirms that stakeholder-driven design works. Insights from more than sixty experts, operators and policy actors have already shaped SCS interfaces, prioritised predictive-maintenance features, and sharpened the narrative around cost and charging—issues consistently ranked as critical adoption drivers. At the same time, the project’s dissemination footprint has grown steadily: web traffic outperformed targets by 40 %, LinkedIn followers surpassed the mid-term goal, and SmartCorners is now cited in cluster newsletters and a peer-reviewed SAE WCX 2025 paper. These achievements translate into a measurable rise in Societal Readiness—from ‘awareness’ to active ‘early-adopter engagement’—reducing market risk for the upcoming demonstrators.

With a robust feedback loop in place and a growing community of supporters, SmartCorners will continue to share results on the project’s modular, upgradeable SCS EV architecture that accelerates Europe’s shift towards zero-emission, user-centric road transport.

11.1 Deviations

A deviation of three weeks has occurred to perform the project steering board review due to the public nature of the deliverable. All milestones and KPIs are on, or ahead of, schedule.

12 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long text
2ZERO	Towards zero emission road transport
AI	Artificial intelligence
CDE	Communication, dissemination, exploitation
EC	European Commission
EGVIA	European Green Vehicles Initiative Association
ERTICO	European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
EV	Electric vehicle
G2M	Go-to-market
ICE	Internal combustion engine
IP	Intellectual property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IWM	In-wheel motor
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NMPC	Nonlinear model predictive control
NNMPC	Neural network model predictive control
SCS	Smart corner systems
SME	Small and medium enterprise
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
WP	Work Package
XIL	X-in-the-Loop

13 Sources

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the European Union**

SmartCorners is an active member of the E-VOLVE Cluster and selected under the “Towards zero emission road transport” partnership (2Zero).

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement Nr. 101138110. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.